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Trains, stations, and railways as harbingers of biopolitics in digital games: From governance to hauntology

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17 **Trains, stations, and railways as harbingers of biopolitics in digital games: From**
18 **governance to hauntology**

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26 stations, and railways from the perspective of the biopolitical theory. We aimed to analyze
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47 **Introduction**

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Positioned in the field of biopolitical reflection within game studies, this article focuses on the ludic representations of trains and rails in selected digital games to argue that the rail medialization in gameworlds preserves, reinforces, and hyperbolizes technological, cultural, and philosophical (hauntological) aspects of biopolitical ideologies embedded in train technology. For the purpose of this study, we operate with a broad understanding of biopolitics proposed by thinkers such as Michel Foucault (2010), Roberto Esposito (2017), and Achille Mbembe (2020) as a field of studies invested in exploring various forms of political, social, and

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3 economic governance over the life of an individual and population. We locate our study within
4 the subfield of biopolitical reflection devoted to researching biopolitical problems within games
5 and gaming culture. In this paper, we focus on the representations of rail in games. We claim
6 that these representations reveal the power structures invested in governance over life, reflect
7 their imperial origins, and mediate ghastly vestiges of rail technology's biopolitical past. Rail
8 has been analyzed in game studies as a medium of imperial governance used to expand
9 territories, and produce center-periphery dynamics (Mukherjee, 2017, p. 44; 2020, p. 176- 180).
10 We continue this line of questioning rail representations by deconstructing the biopolitical
11 aspects of spatial reconfiguration performed by railway infrastructure: metro stations, railways,
12 and trains. Our research material consists of the rail's representation as a medium of progress
13 and its positive and negative anthropological effects (pharmacology) (Stiegler, 2015). The aim
14 of this study is therefore to uncover ludotopian dimensions of game biopolitics generated by
15 the railway, which produces utopian or dystopian spaces (Farca, 2019) and functions as a kernel
16 for power dispositives (Foucault, 2011; Mieszkowski, 2022). By ludotopia we understand the
17 "dialectical entanglement of games and space" (Aarseth & Gunzel 2021, p.7), which we expand
18 to look at games as spaces for governance. The article is part of a wider reflection on game
19 biopolitics and its meaningful elements, called "biopolitical markers" (Kłosiński, 2024, pp. 4-
20 5) allowing researchers to identify diverse assemblages of game mechanics, esthetics, and
21 representations of different paradigms of governing life (Apperley & Clemens, 2016; Mitchell,
22 2018; Rutheford & Bose, 2013).

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The main problem we explore in this study is related to game representations and
remediations of the rail industry. One of the most horrifying and gruesome historical visages of
death camps and politics of death – necropolitics (Mbembe, 2020, pp. 79–92) – is the death
train transporting people to concentration camps. Brenda Romero has critically explored this
theme in her tabletop game *Train* (Romero, 2009), which aims to shock players with the
revelation that their gameplay is an optimization of human transports to Auschwitz (Isbister,
2017, p. 10; Marak et al., 2019, p. 10). However, before the purely necropolitical use of trains,
even the very establishment of the railway system in the 19th century has to be considered a
project rendering imperial governance and politics of control over the populace (Mukherjee,
2017, p. 44). Well-described "railway wars" (Starr, 2012) are an example of this early
necropolitical aspect of imperial infrastructure at work, where dispossession of land and
destruction of buffalo populace played a crucial part in racist infrastructural necropolitics in
both the United States and Canada (Cowen, 2020, p. 476; Ranganathan, 2020, p. 495).

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3 Moreover, the use of “plague trains” in military campaigns and war against epidemics
4 (Mieszkowski, 2022, p. 162) gives further insight into the significance of rail as a historical
5 apparatus of governance over life, health, and public order. This study also encompasses the
6 facilities established as entry and exit points for various types of trains: stations, tunnels, and
7 metro networks. Their biopolitical significance expanded throughout the centuries from
8 metropolitan communication hubs, economic lifeways of modern countries, colonial media,
9 and strategic military assets to concrete underground shelters of the Cold War era and
10 commercial galleries forming underground cities. Most of them are also manifestations of
11 invasive intrusion in the natural environment, and landscape alterations testifying to the
12 biopolitical governance over human and non-human lives alike.

21 As an important element of modernity and its biopolitical projects, rail produces cultural
22 meanings, moves imagination, and inscribes its phantasms into different narratives on society
23 and its structures. From Western train-heists to postapocalyptic metro narratives, rail and its
24 facilities signify a shift in human thinking about the world; they reconfigure how we perceive
25 distance, time, social relations, and urban and industrial regions (McLuhan, 2013). Therefore,
26 as media, technology, and technical objects, rail reorganizes social imaginaries and ways human
27 beings think about time, territory, and social relations (Stiegler, 2009, pp. 90–91), but it also
28 “frames nature” making it a part of human geographical project (Stiegler, 1998, pp. 80–83).
29 Furthermore, it is an apparatus critically linked with questions concerning racism (Karuka,
30 2019), liberalism, and climate change (Das, 2015, pp. 50–60). This is why researching game
31 representations, mechanics, and procedural rhetoric related to rail and its facilities constitutes
32 an important element of game analysis.

42 Looking at the use of rail in games we can distinguish two general sets of titles. One is
43 rail-focused and encompasses train simulators, train arcades, and railway strategy games where
44 the rail is the major gameplay theme: an avatar, phenomenological or existential experience and
45 sole industry to be governed. The other consists of games where rail and its facilities are either
46 optional elements of gameplay (one among many technology tree discoveries) or parts of game
47 ecology (important quest area, landscape, or mode of transportation). This project is devoted to
48 the rail as a biopolitical apparatus and thus will focus not on questions concerning the
49 verisimilitude of simulation or representation, but on the rail as part of a larger experience of
50 the game. In short, we are interested in the ideological and political aspects of rail in games, not
51 the technical aspects of driving a train simulator.

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3 In this study, we identify and analyze different biopolitical aspects of rail in digital
4 games. Some of these aspects overlap with genre-specific mechanics and procedural rhetoric of
5 imperialism (Dyer-Witheford & de Peuter, 2009), neoliberalism (Dooghan, 2019), and
6 colonialism (Mukherjee, 2017), which have been studied as biopolitical problems under
7 different disciplinary umbrella terms (Kłosiński, 2024). Because rail and railways have been
8 described as important elements of real colonization, imperial agency, and biopolitics, we seek
9 to discover how many of those have been remediated and reshaped in games and have become
10 explicit or implicit elements of their signifying strategies. The structure of this article is as
11 follows: in the first part, we focus on rail infrastructure and how it produces and represents
12 social, racial, and community divisions. Afterward, we shift our attention to the railway strategy
13 games in which themes such as imperialism and nationalism are explored against the backdrop
14 of economic or biopolitical struggle. Finally, we explore the hauntological aspects of rail in
15 games, and its mediation of biopolitical phantasms.
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29 **Rail infrastructure and its discontents**

30 In this section, we demonstrate how the rail infrastructure in the *Metro* game series (4A Games,
31 2010, 2013, 2019) represents key aspects of the spatial mediation of life governance.
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34 As a title that immediately comes to mind when thinking about rail infrastructure, *Metro* games
35 remediate and expand Dmitry Glukhovsky's literary universe from the novel *Metro 2033*
36 (Glukhovsky, 2010) and its highly acclaimed sequels. The first two games take the player to
37 the Moscow metro tunnels, the last remaining bastion for humanity after the nuclear holocaust.
38 Thus, the metro infrastructure becomes a dystopian game space (Farca, 2018) where the society
39 is restructured according to the weird postapocalyptic convention and has to live in enclaves
40 forever haunted by deadly mutants roaming the underground. The games perfectly capture the
41 claustrophobic and weblike structure of one of the largest metro installations in the world
42 (Hoedt, 2020), but also, as researchers point out, they render and come into dialogue with the
43 political economy of the Stalinist era, making distinct references to the neoclassical and
44 modernist station design that inspired Glukhovsky's original novels (Bishop, 2020, pp. 316–
45 317). Therefore, it is no surprise that these cultural imaginaries have been read as exemplary
46 for postapocalyptic biopolitics (Nijakowski, 2018, p. 247). In the postapocalyptic world, life is
47 constantly threatened by environmental factors, such as pollution, mutated flora and fauna, and
48 reorganized tribal communities created to survive these new conditions. Biopolitical
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3 governance can be seen in managing the scarcity of resources, constructing barriers and
4 shelters, scavenging, and politics of life staging the conflict between the survival of the fittest
5 on the one hand, and the survival of the community on the other. The basic mechanism in *Metro*
6 games uses signifiers of danger, immunity, and community, which have been turned into
7 affordance indicators for game level design. The metro tunnel network is both a biopolitical
8 system of bunkers shielding humanity from extinction and an intricate web of barriers, zones,
9 and chokepoints used to govern the populace and defend it against mutants. In short, the metro
10 infrastructure becomes the proper apparatus and technology for organizing human and non-
11 human agency, being, and imagination. The metro tunnel system becomes a world for the
12 players to inhabit and explore, and as such, projects affordances and ludotopian ecology
13 (Linderoth, 2013).
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23 Unlike its predecessors, *Metro Exodus*, the third installment in *Metro* game series,
24 expands the narrow tunnel-focused game ecology onto vast open spaces of postapocalyptic
25 wastelands. Here, the railway infrastructure constitutes the most important aspect of building
26 the storyworld and anchoring linear game narration in a quasi-open-world setting. Firstly, the
27 train's name, "Aurora," gives it a symbolic meaning, referring to the goddess of dawn,
28 signifying a new beginning, and hope as well as playing out the binary division between the
29 dusky atmosphere of metro tunnels and a new dawn of the outside world. Furthermore, the
30 name pays homage and serves as a historical linkage to the cruiser Aurora which fired the first
31 shot signaling the onset of the October Revolution. The signification here is straightforward:
32 the train marks a revolutionary moment for the *Metro* series and a critical change in the
33 mentality of Artyom's community. Secondly, the train carriages are indispensable for staging
34 community meetings, narrating friendships and family relations, as well as separating Artyom's
35 crew from all other communities: remnants of the Russian government, religious zealots,
36 cannibals, oil slavers, and newfound tribes. The train becomes a space for habitation,
37 functioning not only as a mobile base of operations, but as a home, immunized from the harsh
38 reality of the postapocalyptic wastelands, radioactive zones, and mutated creatures. This is best
39 seen in scenes of father-son discussions, friendly meetings, time of privacy between Artyom
40 and his wife Anna, and the wedding ceremony of Katya and Stephan. The individual
41 compartments within Aurora are filled with family pictures, souvenirs, and warm lights. They
42 are in stark opposition to the spaces Artyom explores along the way: creepy polluted tunnels
43 filled with rust and decay, impoverished dwellings of fanatics and slaves, or crumbling ruins,
44 ghastly witnesses of inhumanity. The railway infrastructure is therefore less important in this
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3 title than the train itself, mostly functioning to build contrast between the entropic world and
4 ever-progressing Aurora. *Metro Exodus* focuses on representing Aurora as a community hub
5 and immunizing it against the outside dangers (Esposito 2017, p. 12). This community is of
6 course driven by the idea of finding a suitable space to settle down, thus many topics in its
7 discussions concern the biopolitics of reproduction: discussions between Anna and Artyom
8 about having children, Miller constantly nagging them to start “making babies,” even Katya
9 and Stephan conversing with Nastya about a prospect of having another child – a baby brother
10 or sister. Thus, *Metro Exodus* establishes its biopolitics of care, community, and reproduction
11 using the train as both its spatial and symbolic foundation.
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19 The biopolitical aspect of metro infrastructure can therefore be found in the structure
20 which renders social divisions, racial dispositives (human vs. non-human) as well as
21 immunitary logic of enclaves and communities (neo-Nazis vs. neo-communists, Aurora crew
22 vs. the world). Furthermore, the metro tunnels in *Metro* game series become spaces for staging
23 weird phenomena: temporal loops, ghastly trains, phantom interventions, out-of-the-world
24 experiences, and historical flashbacks, and the train symbolically evokes the concept of a
25 revolution. The metro infrastructure functions as a link between postapocalyptic weird fiction
26 and reflection about history, its phantoms, traumas, and inescapable loops. The metro, therefore
27 introduces ghosts as important figures for the games’ ontology and undermines the experience
28 of the world rooted in materiality (Fisher, 2012; Gare, 2016). This aspect is pivotal for the
29 biopolitical design of the ludotopia: it enables reflection about the governmentality in the
30 Stalinist times, evokes critical inquiries into the thanatopolitical aspects of different social
31 organizations, and shows how traumatic past shapes the community to come. Biopolitics can
32 be seen in the design of social spaces and projection of intimacy, the construction of enclaves
33 and their symbolic dimension, as well as economic and political problems that various NPCs
34 constantly narrate in their background stories.
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48 Therefore, *Metro* games use the rail infrastructure to stage experiences related to
49 claustrophobia, a sense of enclosure, confinement, danger, or haunting. This structure exposes
50 players to biopolitical communizing and immunizing mechanisms, representing the logic of
51 generating social divisions. *Metro* games capitalize on rail infrastructure on three levels:
52 affordances of the game space; carrying meanings of immunization and communization
53 processes; and the rail-produced management of time, generating a hauntological experience of
54 exposure to the return of the suppressed past.
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Railway to nationality

This section explores the overlaps between the ludic employments of trains as industrial enterprises as well as means of transportation and the establishment of national identities, ideologies, and hierarchies. This type of railway utilization in games can be exemplified by a free-to-play web browser game *Rail Nation* (Bright Future, 2013), which blends the elements of economic simulation, real-time strategy, and digital museum. The players are put in the position of governors for the railway industry and choose their base of operations among the major US cities belonging to one of two competing factions: West or East, stylized respectively as farmer cowboys and elitist entrepreneurs. It is here that the basic biopolitical premise is constructed for the players: the railway is not just a business, it is a duel for supremacy over the USA, fought between two distinctively exemplified classes of people and their vision of the American dream. In its representations, narrative, and mechanics the game realizes an imperial scheme (Mukherjee, 2017, pp. 33–36; Mukherjee & Hammar, 2018): the fog of war functions as a veillance indicator of the reach of our power of sight; the influence map expresses the idea that business is about monopolizing the industry and pushing out the competition; territorial expansion via building railways and upgrading engines presents the procedural rhetoric of colonization through technological supremacy; the mapping of locations according to their economic utility depicts a vision of reductionist political economy; and finally, the community aspect of the game is built on the idea of corporationalization of power structures and gaining fame by achieving economic goals. In essence, the game uses the railway infrastructure as the kernel of power dispositives; it provides vision and surveillance, control over territory, access to resources, advantage in conflict, and the communization of entrepreneurs. Furthermore, the upgrade mechanics in the free-play model of the game are procedurally linked with real-time and premium, real-money-based currency, which can be used to speed up various in-game actions. This is no longer a representation of the biopolitical power of the rail infrastructure, but governing the players as potential spenders of the real currency (Dyer-Witheford & de Peuter, 2009, p. 126; Lassila, 2022, p. 6). The free-to-play model is built on the idea that players can take surveys and watch advertisements to gain additional premium currency. Thus, *Rail Nation* connects in-game power dispositives: colonization, governance, and struggle for economic domination with mechanics incentivizing players to gain an advantage over others by using their real money or time to watch advertisements. The game economy is based on choosing the most lucrative routes and train schedules to fulfill the needs of a player-governed city. Therefore, the railway infrastructure is presented as an indispensable element of

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3 governance over a city and its population along the lines of the modernist project of
4 industrialization and territorialization – building an interface between geography and technical
5 systems (Stiegler, 2010, p. 128).
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9 The RTS genre-defining economic elements and colonial narrative can also be found in
10 the *Railway Empire* (Gaming Minds Studios, 2018) and its sequel *Railway Empire 2* (Gaming
11 Minds Studios, 2023). The first production offers five game modes with a large narrative
12 campaign inviting players to participate in building the first American transcontinental railroad;
13 the sequel adds continental Europe with its 19th-century geopolitics in the background. Thus,
14 players engage in a playful historical reconstruction (Chapman, 2016) of the endeavor
15 representing the scope of the colonization of North America in the 19th century, and its
16 European counterpart. The game scenarios hint at the colonial project in diegetic narrative
17 elements: newspaper articles and enunciations made by NPC player guides staged as sponsors
18 for our business. No Native Americans ever come into our way in the first game, just as no
19 Chinese workers or Black Americans are represented in the game’s vivid art style – the game
20 is “white” in its mechanics, representations, and narratives. This procedural rhetoric shows the
21 underlying biopolitical structure of hydraulic or nanoracism – performing racial segregation in
22 broad daylight while presenting colonizers and the state as sworn to neutrality and tolerance
23 (Mbembe, 2020, p. 59). What this whitewashing of American colonization (Karuka, 2019, pp.
24 170–173) serves is the predominant political economy underlying the game’s mechanics, an
25 ideological whitewashing of the liberal doctrine in which building railway infrastructure is
26 presented as an economic battle fueled by competition and belief in technological evolution.
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40 As argued by Ryan Dearing, the rhetorical significance of railways as one of the
41 “internal improvement projects” that would “transform America into a powerful continental
42 empire, and raise up God’s kingdom on earth” (Dearing, 2016, p. 21) was enormous in the
43 19th century. Simultaneously, the twisted core of the said rhetoric was that “American citizens
44 . . . used canals, railroads, and the wilderness they ostensibly conquered to rehash notions of
45 civilization, to reconstruct boundaries of citizenship and manhood, and to distance the work of
46 unskilled immigrants while praising the industrial progress they helped create” (Dearing,
47 2016, p. 25). The workforce erasure in *Railway Empire* seems, therefore, aligned with an
48 established imperial discourse. The game displays a handful of biopolitical significations by
49 choosing not to display them, or by conveniently failing to represent the actors captured in the
50 web of state apparatuses and colonial politics.
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3 What the *Railway Empire* games focus on is presenting the positive aspects of
4 governmentality connected with railway infrastructure: the major mechanics are related to
5 building stations near resource production facilities to bring those resources into nearby
6 settlements, fulfill their needs, and thus invite their populations to grow and prosper. Moreover,
7 the games calculate players' business worth and allow them to wage war on the stock market
8 to monopolize competition by merging or buying their businesses. The governmental
9 dispositives here explicitly show that the absolute aim of our business is monopoly in the region.
10 The games offer a handful of supplementary mechanics that function as necropolitical elements:
11 inciting train robbery, sabotage, bribing or outbidding personnel, stealing research, and
12 destroying public trust with journalist slander. Players can decide not to use any explicitly
13 destructive dispositives, but here is where the real biopolitical struggle happens: the procedural
14 rhetoric of railway stations and rail placement invites players to block competition out of
15 particular areas through aggressive zoning strategies and pure dark play (Sicart, 2015, p. 110).
16 These form the core of the governmental, monopolist rhetoric: blocking passages, securing
17 better coverage of businesses, and buying companies that our competitors failed to sustain due
18 to our actions. The *Railway Empire* games not only masterfully narrate economic conflict with
19 procedures, but also exhibit the procedural nature of biopolitics: it turns all that is communal
20 and social into data and statistics (Christiansen, 2014, p. 5). This is true for all RTS and RPG
21 games which simulate economy by simplifying all communal aspects and morality to the
22 market logic of accumulation, yet the *Railway Empire* games do it so openly that it becomes
23 what Seth Giddens calls a microcosmic model of neoliberal forces (Giddings, 2018, p. 770).
24 What seems striking from the contemporary perspective is that the influence of the rail industry
25 on the environment is not even considered in these games, while scientific inquiries into railway
26 infrastructure show their catastrophic impact on the biosphere (Das, 2015).
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45 A different approach to biopolitical problems related to rail management and nationality
46 has been the focus of the *Last Train Home* (Ashborne Games, 2023), a survival real-time
47 strategy game narrating the story of a Czechoslovakian Legion revolt in 1918 and its evacuation
48 in 1920, taking the Trans-Siberian railway to return from Russia during the aftermath of World
49 War I and amidst the Russian Civil War. The story is narrated by a "historian" introducing the
50 game as a work of fiction based on historical documents left by one of the Legionnaires.
51 Through simple tasks such as collecting fuel for the engine, food, and supplies, repairing
52 infrastructure, and helping the local populace, the players experience the horrors of the country
53 torn by the civil war and governed under the state of exception (Agamben, 2005, p. 23). The
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3 game focuses on community survival and presents the Czechoslovakian Legion as the main
4 group to care for and immunize against external threats. The game operates with a plethora of
5 biopolitical markers, from the health, morale, and stamina of each legionnaire to general
6 biopolitical upgrades of the train capacity to protect and sustain life in harsh winter
7 environments of Russia: carriage heating, protection of food against rodents, hygiene and health
8 systemic solutions like day/night shifts, food rationing, sleeping conditions. Furthermore, the
9 *Last Train Home* combines RTS veillance signifiers such as fog of war, or god-like insight into
10 the political beliefs of our subordinates, with stealth mechanics (cones of vision, sneaking) and
11 their thanatopolitical use in stealth kills. Because the game focuses on presenting a quasi-
12 historical narrative about the survival and struggles of the Czechoslovakian Legion, it operates
13 with signifiers of community and immunity mostly in narrative elements and community
14 governance mechanics: our legionnaires are sent on missions where we decide to help or doom
15 local communities suffering from the horrors of the civil war, and we must upgrade our train to
16 fit all additional legionnaires we find on our way to Vladivostok – if our train does not have
17 space to accommodate them, we decide who stays back forever. The game also provides us
18 with a memorial of the fallen and abandoned soldiers, strengthening the choice and consequence
19 design and its lasting effects on our train community.

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Lastly, the game operates with numerous thanatopolitical signifiers: from different
weapon choices and killing strategies to representations of civil war extremities and genocide.
The players govern a legion and the game produces the narrative of a sieged community that
needs immunization against external threats (the Reds, climate, diseases, mental distress) and
depends on proper governance of major supplies such as coal, metal, cloth, lumber, food,
medication as well as military equipment. The stake of the game's narrative is the return to the
titular home – a new nation awaiting the faithful legionnaires. Thus, their engagement in the
events of the civil war in Russia is measured against the problematic political situation of a
neutral army outside the national boundaries, in a territory under the state of exception
(Agamben, 2005, pp. 3–4, 2005, p. 32), where the rule of law is suspended. The struggles of
our community are therefore represented as nostalgia-driven on the one hand, and biopolitically
subordinate to the logic of the state of exception on the other. The rail mechanics and
affordances masterfully capture this conundrum – unlike other empire-building games, in the
Last Train Home we do not conquer land or spread our influence. All our agency conveyed by
the game narrative and mechanics is focused on the biopolitical governance of a cultural melting
pot of Czechoslovaks where we desperately try to save as many legionnaires as possible. In this

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3 sense, the train has been fully utilized as a biopolitical and community-building device, similar
4 to how it functioned in *Metro: Exodus*, but instead of a pure survival orientation, it now serves
5 as a rail to nationality.
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10 11 **Rail that haunts** 12

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14 The third set of examples deals with games in which biopolitical forces, while not reliant on
15 trains, manifest and affect player characters partly thanks to the hauntological properties of
16 railroad networks and railway tracks, connected with their liminality. As noted by John Urry,
17 railroads blur boundaries between “the route and the vehicle” (Urry, 2012, p. 93), passengers
18 and cargo (Urry, 2012, p. 94), as well as space as a tangible place and transitory experience
19 (Urry, 2012, p. 93). As a historical development, the common use of trains altered spatial
20 perception by “bringing some places closer together and . . . connecting places that otherwise
21 would have never been connected” (Urry, 2012, p. 100). Simultaneously, the mass introduction
22 of train schedules not only constituted “a powerful system of governmentality” (Urry, 2012, p.
23 98), but also reinforced “the orientation to time as a resource to be managed rather than to time
24 as activity and meaning” (Urry, 2012, p. 99), undermining the relevance of “kairological time,”
25 focused on the significance of the present moment (Urry, 2012, p. 98). It is, perhaps, such a
26 tendency to undermine the here and now that additionally imbues railway infrastructure with
27 an hauntological aura. As Mark Fisher puts it, with the use of Martin Hagglund’s phrasing,
28 hauntology revolves around the “virtual agency of the *no longer*” (Fisher, 2012, p. 21, original
29 italics) or the “*not yet*” (Fisher, 2012, p. 19, original italics) – a pressure which, in Jacques
30 Derrida’s words, results in a “dis-located time of the present” (Derrida, 2006, p. 20), a
31 “disjointed or disadjusted now” (Derrida, 2006, p. 1). In one of the games discussed in this
32 section, *Life Is Strange* (Dontnod Entertainment, 2015), railway tracks become carriers for the
33 haunting pressure of the past and the future on the present, effectively undermining the
34 ontological status of the player’s experience. It is, however, worth noticing that the ghostly
35 predispositions of trains and railroads can be treated by games much more literally, as
36 exemplified by the case of *Hard West 2* (Ice Code Games, 2022) or, to the point of caricature,
37 in *Choo-Choo Charles* (Two Star Games, 2022), in which the supernatural seems to bring out
38 the biopolitical significance of trains and railroads as such.
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57 *Hard West 2* is an isometric tactical RPG which, as a typical representative of the Weird
58 West genre, mixes and combines the most characteristic tropes and attributes of the gothic and
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3 Western. The two conventions are spectacularly brought together in the game prologue, in
4 which the player character and the criminal gang he is the leader of carry out a train robbery
5 only to discover that they are aboard a supernatural “Ghost Train.” Forced to confront the devil
6 in charge of the train, they eventually escape it, but lose their souls in the process, which
7 generates the main game quest of finding the vehicle and retrieving the missing spiritual
8 elements. A quasi-biopolitical consideration of the frame quest is possible, as the protagonists
9 are driven by the loss of control over a vital part of their identities. In addition, however, the
10 very idea of a spectral train seems to have its own biopolitical significance traceable back to its
11 liminal character.
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19 American folklore knows a number of ghost-train tales, mostly connected with specific
20 historical events, like the story of Abraham Lincoln’s funeral train, or region transformations,
21 like the “Ghost Train of the Santa Ana” tale, in which the supernatural is attached to a railway
22 connection abandoned for the sake of progress (Swayne, 2019). It might, however, be argued
23 that the very biopolitical, as well as hauntological potential of technology and progress
24 represented by the railway makes trains not only susceptible objects, but also suitable agents of
25 haunting. As mentioned in the previous sections, their presence in the American West testified,
26 among other things, to the necropolitics aimed at the local indigenous peoples, rival companies,
27 and natural environment, as well as the oppressive biopower targeting railway workers; it also
28 signaled the impending crisis of the agrarian myth of the Frontier (Slotkin, 1998, pp. 215–216).
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37 When Derrida writes about “tele-technology” which implicates “the virtualization of
38 space and time, the possibility of virtual events whose movement and speed prohibit us more
39 than ever . . . from opposing presence to its representation, . . . in short, the living to the living-
40 dead of its ghosts” (Derrida, 2006, p. 212), he refers to media (Fisher, 2012, p. 19). By doing
41 so, he subscribes – as Fisher notices – to a broader postmodern claim that, thanks to the
42 developing communication technologies, “[e]vents that are spatially distant become available
43 to audience instantaneously” (Fisher, 2012, p. 19). Although different in origin, the impact of
44 media on the perception of space seems to produce a similar, though understandably more
45 intense effect to that of railway technology as discussed by Urry: “the railway appeared to create
46 its own space linking many different places (while of course excluding others) into ever more
47 complex and extended systems of speeded-up circulation” (Urry, 2012, p. 101).
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57 Therefore, the board of a “Ghost Train” as the setting for the prologue, as well as the
58 epilogue of a Weird West game seems adequate in more ways than one. The supernatural
59 character of the spectral machine brings out its liminality and hyperbolizes its power to connect
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3 places. In the opening scene, the protagonists attack what looks like a regular train, only for it
4 to transform into a demonic vehicle after crossing a tunnel whose sudden appearance suggests
5 a passage between the worlds. Further in the game, the train is confirmed to travel between
6 realities and harvest multiple mortal souls whenever it enters the Hard West realm. While the
7 player character and his companions manage to secure theirs, it remains uncertain if they
8 manage to get out of the otherworld that the Ghost Train has dragged them into. Thus, in *Hard*
9 *West 2*, the narrative demonization of the train seems to resonate with the actual potential of
10 “the railway [to] restructur[e] the existing relations between nature, time and space” (Urry,
11 2012, p. 94).

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19 *Choo-Choo Charles*, in turn, seems to achieve a vast part of its supernatural horror by
20 transgressing or subverting more immediate biopolitical properties of trains. The game is a first-
21 person shooter, in which the player character moves around an island in a small, armed train
22 engine, searching for a way to defeat Charles – a monstrous train engine with spider legs, which
23 is known to devour the locals. The very idea of a human-eating train may be seen as a twist on
24 the actual function of that means of transportation, in which “the human body becomes like an
25 anonymized parcel of flesh” (Urry, 2012, p. 94). Thus, the main difference between a regular
26 train and Charles is that he does not spit people back.

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34 Another source of horror is located in the monster’s hybridity (Švelch, 2023, pp. 74–
35 76), allowing its animalistic features and habits to counter the predictability of a machine. As
36 noted by Urry, “[t]hese [industrial] machines are typically confined to specific and highly
37 regulated sites residing outside everyday life, such as the factory, workshop, railway track, dock
38 and so on. When the machine is not in motion they are stored within specialized, guarded sites
39 with the public kept out” (Urry, 2012, p. 93). Anthropod-like, Charles not only manifests basic
40 behaviors of a living creature, such as feeding and procreation – by laying eggs – but also
41 escapes into hiding and recovers in nature if he suffers too much damage from a confrontation
42 with humans. Thanks to his fast and sudden movements guaranteed by the spider-like
43 appendages, the monster’s mobility is astounding and not limited to the track routes. Charles’
44 appearances often have a jump-scare effect when he abruptly materializes on the tracks and
45 starts chasing the player character’s engine, only to get lost in the landscape again. The player
46 character can leave their vehicle, and does so mainly to enter specific locations, such as a local
47 settlement or mine, talk to the locals, collect materials for engine improvement, or carry out
48 specific quests. Still, the main exploration of the island depends on the railway tracks, which
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3 also become the stage for most fights with Charles, as the only effective weapon against him is
4 a machine gun installed at the back of the player character's small train engine.
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8 Therefore, one source of the game's horror is constituted by mockingly recontextualized
9 biopolitical aspects of train travel: human beings given the status of organic cargo, and
10 confinement to railway as the only possible path for movement. Charles' animalism disturbing
11 the predictability of a machine plays with both of them by turning him into a human-eating
12 monster that can jump on and off the tracks on his own volition. While the very concept of a
13 train monster resonates with the trope of a ghost or haunted train as the most widespread way
14 of inducing that means of transport with the supernatural, it is the other, more gameplay-
15 oriented source of horror located in the game's genre that seems more susceptible to a
16 hauntological reading. As noted by Klaudia Jancsovics, claustrophobic depiction of space is a
17 device characteristic of horror games (Jancsovics, 2022, p. 76), and, in the case of *Choo-Choo*
18 *Charles*, the partial confinement to tracks seems to reinforce that effect. The moments Charles
19 suddenly bursts into chase after the player character's engine unquestionably build up tension
20 in accordance with Jancsovics' emphasis on the player's constant anticipation of threat as an
21 important factor in games of horror (2022, p. 74). The resultant gameplay atmosphere may be
22 interpreted as a graspable, if not very subtle, experience of the "disjointed... now" (Derrida,
23 2006, p. 1), central to the hauntological effect, as the anticipation of each particular encounter
24 with Charles turns the perception of "now" into "now, or not yet?" Simultaneously, such
25 perception shifts also seem in line with the systemic depreciation of experiencing the present
26 that Urry ascribes to train infrastructure (Urry, 2012, p. 98).
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41 An episodic, but strikingly relevant engagement of railway in a much more complex
42 scrutiny of time segmentation and biopolitical consequences of its impact on the present takes
43 place in *Life Is Strange*. It is an almost entirely story-driven game with the main mechanics,
44 apart from dialog choices and point-and-click exploration of the surroundings, based on the use
45 of the player character's supernatural power to "rewind" time. The frame narrative around
46 Max's temporal powers and the game's main plotline has a spectacular thanatopolitical
47 dimension generated by the enforcement of the choice to save some lives by sacrificing others
48 (Lemm, 2013, pp. 6–7). The first time the protagonist undoes the events of the most immediate
49 past is to save her friend, Chloe – and, as is gradually revealed, the resultant alteration of reality
50 causes an escalation of events which eventually threatens to destroy the entire town. That is
51 why, by the end of the game, Max has to make a thanatopolitical choice between her friend and
52 the population of Arcadia Bay, as allowing Chloe's death prevents the town destruction, while
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3 saving her results in a natural disaster that leaves the town in ruin and kills many of its
4 inhabitants. Thus, in *Life Is Strange*, the burden of unpredictable consequences, often attached
5 to the temporal manipulation trope, is rendered not so much in terms of a scientific paradox, as
6 rather a personalized take on the trolley problem, in which Max's time-changing power proves
7 thanatopolitical in its impact on who is going to live and who is not.
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12 Seemingly, none of the game's major themes involves trains or railroads. However, a
13 scene featuring both of them is simultaneously a striking moment of thanatopolitical
14 foreshadowing in which the experience of "killing" vs. saving Chloe subtly shifts its weight
15 from the narrative to the gameplay level, reaching out to the player's somatic and emotional
16 engagement. In the second of the game's five episodes, the friends spend some time at a
17 scrapyard and proceed to explore a nearby railroad. As Chloe's foot gets stuck between the
18 tracks, a train shows up and Max has to work out how to set her friend free before she is run
19 over. Discovering how to rescue Chloe within the limited scope of the gameworld's affordances
20 becomes a gameplay challenge for the player. As the only solution is based on a chain reaction
21 involving several objects scattered around the area and depending on the player's right guesses,
22 immediate success is unlikely. Therefore, the game forms a loop in which Chloe keeps dying
23 under the train's wheels, and Max keeps undoing that moment until the player, hurried by
24 Chloe's panicked shouts, resolves all stages of the puzzle.
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35 While doing it at the first attempt is theoretically possible, the player will likely be
36 forced to accept Chloe's repeated deaths to find the solution and ultimately save her. Such an
37 action might be argued to give the player a more tangible thanatopolitical experience than
38 Max's choice between her friend and Arcadia Bay. In the latter case, Chloe's life is weighed
39 against the existence of a population, while in the former, the girl is temporarily sacrificed for
40 the sake of her own eventual survival. Therefore, the railroad incident can be seen as a
41 foreshadowing of Max's ultimate choice, which – being less significant in narrative, but more
42 intense in gameplay terms – makes the player experience the weight of thanatopolitical
43 responsibility.
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51 The tracks become a stage for a "haunting," which, according to Mark Fisher, "happens
52 . . . when a particular place becomes the site for an encounter with broken time" (Fisher, 2012,
53 p. 19). The time during Chloe's railroad accident is fractured into repeated sequences of almost
54 identical events until her life can be saved. It also highlights Max's role as a wielder of her
55 friend's fate, which the player character is yet to fully embrace by choosing between her and
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3 Arcadia Bay. The “haunting,” therefore, though conditioned by the past act of rescuing Chloe
4 in the school bathroom, shifts towards the future exerting pressure on the present.
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9 10 **Conclusion**

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12 This article aimed to describe and identify biopolitics in representations and procedural rhetoric
13 of rail in digital games. We wanted to see if and how games remediate and simulate biopolitical
14 problems associated with rail technology and infrastructure. The analysis of four titles explicitly
15 related to rail showed an interesting pattern. The *Metro* game series operated mostly with
16 representations of thanatopolitics, immunity, and community, whereas the strategy games were
17 dominated by signifiers of biopolitical representations and mechanics. Furthermore, while the
18 player is made to observe the community building and immunizing power of the railway
19 infrastructure in the *Metro* shooters, and operate with interfaces that inform them about the
20 dangerous power of being in enemy sight, the strategy games operationalize veillance as an
21 element of biopolitical representations and mechanics which are targeted at community
22 building and immunization. While the thanatopolitical signifiers confirm the dominant
23 teleology of the shooters, the railway economic games completely reduce them to narratives
24 referencing biopower or – in one extreme but important case – hydraulic racism.
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35 The combinations of trains and the supernatural, in turn, facilitate the exploration of
36 railways’ spectral qualities which bring out their raw biopower connected with the control over
37 human bodies on the one hand, and broader preoccupation with temporal aspects of biopolitics
38 on the other. The monstrosity of trains, prominent in *Hard West 2* and *Choo-Choo Charles*,
39 hyperbolizes the ways they physically contain and relocate passengers’ bodies, largely passive
40 and vulnerable in those processes, as well as destined to reach specific, not necessarily – as
41 indicated also by some other cases discussed in the paper – welcoming locations.
42 Simultaneously, all three games aestheticize or fictionalize time perception deformations
43 characteristic of train travel, such as the ambivalent status of the present moment, segmentation
44 and repetitiveness of the time flow, as well as the pressure of the past or future. All those factors
45 have biopolitical significance as means of governance aimed at individual lives, as well as the
46 management of human masses in flux. Moreover, the power of their impact on cultural
47 imagination is reflected in the connections the analyzed games build between trains, rail, and
48 the experience of temporal collapse.
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3 Our analysis demonstrates that the very presence of railway infrastructure in games
4 mediates a plethora of biopolitical aspects of rail, and railway technology associated with its
5 real, historical impact on human society: from new forms of governance over time and space
6 provided by railway technology's weblike structure connecting stations, places, times and
7 people; to the codification of imperial expansionist ideology in the service of national and
8 economic goals; to hauntological imaginations resurfacing with the ghosts of those who
9 suffered or died because of this technology – natives who stood in its path, workers who built
10 it, those whose lives were displaced by its geopolitical and military impact. With rail, all the
11 aforementioned problems are incorporated into the fabric of each analyzed game, and ludified.
12 Their game medialization is relevant in that it brings out the biopolitical entanglements of rail
13 in the meaning-making practices of producing playable environments. The analyzed games
14 produce original meanings related to community and immunity dynamics, imperialism,
15 historiosophy, traumatic past, and economic governance over land and population by
16 capitalizing on the existing anthropological effects of rail. All in all, the survey of game
17 examples contained in our discussion suggests that the rail, however employed in the digital
18 game worldbuilding, constitutes a powerful biopolitical device for structuring not only space
19 and time, but also existential imagination.
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